

Evaluation of the SED Student Forum on Maximizing Online Learning through Active Learners' Engagement: The Student Experience

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How to cite this paper:

Taja-on, E., and Miras, R. (2021). Evaluation of the SED Student Forum on Maximizing Online Learning through Active Learners' Engagement: The Student Experience. *School of Education Research Journal*, 2(1), 116-137. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29083.18726>

Received: November 19, 2021

Accepted: November 21, 2021

Published: November 22, 2021

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the SED student forum on maximizing online learning through active learners' engagement based on the experiences of students. A mixed-method design was employed to analyze both quantitative and qualitative data. It was conducted to a conveniently sampled 62 Education students from all levels and specializations of the School of Education, San Isidro College. A self-administered questionnaire consisting of open-ended and closed-ended questions was developed and delivered to respondents via Google Form. The responses were tallied. Frequency count, percentages, and mean were used to treat numerical data, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed and interpreted. Overall, the SED student forum was rated excellent by the SED students, and thus, has a high impact on them. Half of the student-respondents suggested optimizing learning during the pandemic as the topic of the next student forum. Students prefer face-to-face learning the most, as the modality to be offered during the new normal setup. They like the learning modalities being offered because of its flexibility but dislike the internet-and technical-related problems that come along with online and digital offline learning. The administration, faculty members, and students take the necessary measures to improve learning during a pandemic and increase the confidence and acceptance of students on the current learning modalities.

Subject Area

Learning Engagement

Keywords: *Online Learning; Learners' Engagement; Online Student Engagement; Student Forum*

INTRODUCTION

Student forums is an integral part of the total experience of students in their learning, especially for education students. With the current pandemic, student forums and other activities are conducted online. Online forums can help student be informed at the comforts of their home and enhance students learning as provided by the institution (Seethamraju, 2014). Student forum evaluation provide relevant information to further improve the overall quality and experience for students (Wisniewski, Zierer, and Hattie, 2020).

To prepare the education students for the “new normal” setup, the School of Education (SED) organized a student forum. It is believed that a student forum is an integral part of the total experience of students in their learning, especially for education students. Through a forum, students can bank on interaction as students receive essential input for knowledge building. A well-coordinated educational forum is a valuable tool in promoting reflective learning, sharing of perspectives, and connecting learners (Benbunan-Fich & Hiltz, 1999; as cited in de Lima, et al., 2019). With the current pandemic, student forums and other activities are conducted online.

Online fora can help the students be informed at the comforts of their home and enhance students' learning as provided by the institution (Seethamraju, 2014). With the rapid development of technology that aids education, online forums have become a tool to promote student critical thinking and knowledge construction (Lim & Chai 2004; Marra, Moore & Klimczak 2004). Additionally, Chinedu (2008) expresses that by participating in online fora, access to knowledge is free, and posits that forum members could willingly share their wealth of knowledge and experience with other members. In return, every member of the forum can benefit from this infusion of free knowledge.

This academic year, the forum organized by SED centered on how to maximize online learning through active learner engagement. Fink (2003) describes a holistic view of active learning that includes all of the following components: Information and Ideas, Experience, and Reflective Dialogue. Meanwhile, Allen and Tanner (2005) explain active learning as “seeking new information, organizing it in a way that is meaningful, and having the chance to explain to others” (p. 262). Studies have shown that employing such methods of active learning improves both students’ learning and their attitudes towards learning (Vygotsky, 1978; Armbruster et. al, 2009). However, many faculties still face challenges when integrating active learning into their lessons. Hence, experimentation and exploration in teaching and learning methods are required to develop and adapt unique teaching methods to a course - including those being taught online (Rogers, 2010).

To ensure the accomplishment of the goals and objectives of the said student forum, student participants were asked to evaluate the event. Evaluation such as this will provide relevant information to further improve the overall quality and experience for students (Wisniewski, Zierer, and Hattie, 2020). This evaluation which capitalizes on students’ experience will help the School of Education determine whether the event was successful according to the goals set, and can help in deciding more effective initiatives for the future facilitation of the event. By soliciting students’ feedback, SED administrators can reflect on the positive elements of the event and consider changes and improvements of the future.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Student evaluation, which may involve computer-aided analysis, is used by academic institutions as a normal practice of soliciting meaningful insights from the students in order to design appropriate interventions or improve the current system. The ultimate goal is to enhance students' learning by ensuring the success of the implemented program/intervention/innovation (Dietz-Uhler & Hurn, 2013; Brennan & William, 2004). Through conducting evaluations, students' feedback could be gathered and analyzed.

Feedback is learning (Biggs, 1999). Feedback is further elaborated on as information with which a learner can confirm, add to, overwrite, tune or restructure information in memory, whether that information is domain knowledge, metacognitive knowledge, beliefs about self and tasks, or cognitive tactics and strategies (Butler & Winne, 1995). Consequently, Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick (2006) had taken feedback as information about how the students' present state (of learning and performance) relates to the goals and expected standards of the course. In other words, it is also illustrated as the 'consequence' of a performance (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). In this study, feedback is interpreted as a pedagogical tool that bridges the student's current level to the expected level set by the course.

In higher education, the importance of feedback has been widely acknowledged. Feedback is often termed as "the most important aspect of the assessment process in raising achievement" (Bloxham & Boyd, 2007). In fact, the students in higher education have regarded feedback as a vital component in shaping and improving their learning experience (Covic & Jones, 2008; Price, Handley, Millar & O' Donovan, 2010; Williams & Kane, 2009; Yorke, 2003).

Indeed, the feedback from students will help the academe take note of their program's strengths and weaknesses to make appropriate changes to the program management. The feedback is also important for curriculum design and management decisions (Denson, et al., 2010). Hence, capturing and analyzing the quantitative and qualitative feedback data from students can provide valuable insights that can be beneficial to the whole institution (El-Halees, 2011).

The design of the conceptual framework capitalizes on the evaluation of the SED Student Forum to reveal students' feedback on four different areas: the impact of the lecture conducted; the topics suggested for the next forum; students' preferred delivery mode; and their likes and dislikes with the learning delivery.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study assessed the evaluation of the SED students on the student's forum on maximizing online learning through active learners' engagement held last May 7, 2021. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the evaluation of the SED students on the impact of the lecture conducted during the student forum?
2. What are the suggested topics that the students wanted to have for their next student forum?
3. What are the preferences of the SED students on the delivery of their lessons this new normal?
4. What do the students like and dislike with the learning delivery that could maximize their learning engagement?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at San Isidro College, a private educational institution in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, established in 1949 by Fr. Joseph Reith, S.J. The school whose patron saint is St. Isidore, offers Teaching Education programs, among other course offerings. The School of Education (SED) includes the following degrees: Bachelor of Secondary Education, majors in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Values Education, and Bachelor of Elementary Education. The school is duly accredited by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and is a member of the Philippine Association for Teachers and Educators (PAFTE).

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the SED faculty delivers lessons through the face-to-face learning modality wherein students have to physically attend classes being conducted inside the school premises. During the pandemic, or "new normal", SED offers two specific modalities: Modular instruction and Online instruction.

Modular instruction is when students receive either digital copies of self-learning modules via Google classroom or printed copies of the modules which students regularly get in the school. The modules will contain the objectives, lesson content, and assessments. Online instruction is when students regularly attend Google Meet or Zoom video conferences and teachers virtually lecture or discuss lessons and interact with students synchronously or asynchronously.

The respondents of this study were 62 students from the School of Education who participated during the school-organized Student Forum on Maximizing Online Learning through Active Learners' Engagement last May 7, 2021, via Google Meet video conferencing. These respondents were conveniently sampled based on their availability to answer the Google Form questionnaire.

This study used a mixed-method approach for in-depth gathering and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data. Furthermore, it utilized a questionnaire delivered to respondents through Google Form. The form enabled the students to evaluate the activity according to the parameters set using the Likert Scale. The quantitative data were then processed statistically using mean, frequency counts, and percentages. Furthermore, open-ended questions were asked to students in order to gather their suggestions, likes, and dislikes. The qualitative data were thematically analyzed through coding and recording patterns or themes.

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Part I of the questionnaire was about students' evaluation on the impact of the SED Student Forum based on five parameters: clarity of learning outcomes, attainment of learning outcomes, mastery of subject matter, presentation and delivery, and appropriateness of material. The criteria used the following:

5	4.21 – 5.00	<i>Excellent</i>	<i>Very High Impact</i>
4	3.40 – 4.19	<i>Very Good</i>	<i>High Impact</i>
3	2.60 – 3.39	<i>Good</i>	<i>Moderate Impact</i>
2	1.80 – 2.59	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	<i>Low Impact</i>
1	1.00 – 1.79	<i>Poor</i>	<i>Very Low Impact</i>

The other parts of the questionnaire were composed of open-ended questions. Specifically, part II was an open-ended question on the topics the respondents have thought about for future online forums. These suggestions could be a basis on designing future student forums which are based on the needs and preferences of students. Part III was a question on respondents' preferred learning modality in the new normal. Finally, part IV asked students to identify their likes and dislikes of the learning delivery that could maximize their learning engagements.

The Google Form questionnaire was administered to students upon the completion of the Student Forum, whereby student-participants were sent the link to the questionnaire via the School of Education Facebook group chat. They were oriented on the importance of their evaluation for future student forums. The responses were then tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of SED students on the student forum under five parameters

Table 1 summarizes the evaluation of the students during the SED student forum last May 7, 2021, according to the parameters set by detailing the percentage of student responses per parameter. It reveals that for the five parameters, students' responses for each range from 3, which is interpreted as 'Good', to 5, 'Excellent'. No respondent rated the event as poor or needing improvement. Therefore, the student forum, which was delivered through a webinar context due to the distance-related limitations of the new normal, was positively viewed by students as evident in the range of their responses.

Table 1. Evaluation of students on the SED student forum

Parameter	Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1
Clarity of learning outcomes	54.8	33.9	11.3	0	0
Attainment of learning outcomes	54.8	35.5	9.7	0	0
Mastery of subject matter	69.4	25.8	4.8	0	0
Presentation and delivery	71.0	24.2	4.8	0	0
Appropriateness of material	61.3	32.3	6.4	0	0

Legend: 5 *Excellent* 4 *Very Good* 3 *Good* 2 *Needs Improvement* 1 *Poor*

Table 2 presents the mean and qualifying description of the different parameters set for the SED student forum. All five parameters were evaluated as 'Excellent' by the student-respondents. The overall mean is 4.67, 'Excellent', meaning students evaluated the SED Student Forum to have a very high impact on them. These findings not only show that the students view the forum with a

positive light, but also the fact that the student forum was a successful learning experience for the attendees, especially as they navigate around the highs and lows of the new normal setup.

Table 2. Summary of the SED student forum

Parameter	Mean	Qualifying Description
Clarity of learning outcomes	4.44	Excellent
Attainment of learning outcomes	4.45	Excellent
Mastery of subject matter	4.65	Excellent
Presentation and delivery	4.66	Excellent
Appropriateness of material	4.55	Excellent
Overall Total	4.67	Excellent

The results show that the use of online environments (e.g., video-conferencing technologies for webinars) could be advantageous when managed wisely. According to Gegenfurter et al. (2017), the synchronous setup makes it possible for participants to communicate directly with their instructors who can provide immediate feedback. Also, the modality allows for real-time group collaboration between participants to occur (Wang & Hsu, 2008; Siewiokek & Gegenfurter, 2010; Johnson & Schumacher, 2016; Gegenfurter et al., 2019a).

Indeed, through a virtual student forum, participants were able to directly interact with the lecturers without the need for them to be in the same physical location. This geographic flexibility and ubiquity could be taken as one of the reasons why amidst the nature of the lecture delivery, the forum was overall rated as Excellent by student-respondents.

Among the parameters evaluated, the parameter with the highest mean is “presentation and delivery”, followed by “mastery of subject matter” trailing only by one mean point. These, among other parameters, were rated excellent. This indicates that the lecture delivered during the Student Forum was well-presented and delivered by the lecturer who has a thorough grasp of the subject and was kept abreast with the trends in education. Therefore, since the lectures were “excellent”, they were effective in marking a very high impact on students.

An effective lecture efficiently transfers knowledge to students by enhancing their conceptual understanding and retention of knowledge (Suter et al., 1998; Fry et al., 2002; Feldon, 2010). To achieve these goals, students should be motivated to be interested in and focus their attention on a lecture. A lecture could be considered effective if the visual and verbal message were clear and the physical presence of the lecturer was evident. The maximization of multimedia resources could also encourage active learning among the participants.

Topics suggested by the students for the next student forum

Figure 2 displays the overview of the topics for future online forums and the frequency of the main themes. As one of the goals of the evaluation is to solicit students’ recommendations on topics for future reference, five major themes were recorded, which are as follows: (1) Optimizing Learning during the Pandemic, (2) Coping Strategies in the New Normal, (3) Student-Teacher Engagement, (4) Time Management and (5) Scholarship (arranged in decreasing order of frequency). Through these responses, the School of Education has baseline data for perusal on the possible topics for the next Student Forum, since these responses were extracted from what the students viewed as the areas needing more input and opportunities for learning.

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Figure 2. Overview of the thematic chart for future online forum

Matrix 1 listed the main themes and sub-themes of future topics for online fora. Examples of the verbatim responses of students were extracted to support the sub-themes and themes listed.

Matrix 1. Summary of qualitative themes for future online forum

Themes	Sub-themes	Theme/ Sub-theme example
Optimizing Learning during the Pandemic	Learning Strategies in the New Normal	<i>“The strategies for good learning process to happen using Online platforms”</i>
	Adjusting to Online Learning	<i>“How to adjust for the new online learning”</i>
	Managing Modular Learning	<i>“Elaborating modular learning”</i>
Coping Strategies in the New Normal	Self-Esteem	<i>“Student’s self-esteem in this new platform of learning”</i>
	Mental Health	<i>“topics about the depression and anxieties that the students are getting and the adjustment that are needed”</i>
Student Teacher Engagement	Teaching Strategies	<i>“Different teaching strategies”</i>
	Evaluating Online Learning	<i>“Tips to evaluate student learning in this online class”</i>
Time Management		<i>“How to manage time”</i>
Scholarship		<i>“About scholarship’s”</i>

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Optimizing Learning during the Pandemic. This theme has three subthemes, namely learning strategies in the new normal, adjusting to online learning, and managing modular learning. The student-respondents wish to be more versatile and capable of learning during the pandemic regardless of their chosen modality. Both modular and online learning has their perks

and drawbacks, and being able to manage the gap in between could make learning more meaningful and efficient for the learners.

To optimize learning during the pandemic, several interlinked factors have to be examined. These factors affect students' experiences and retention: time management skills; the ability to balance work and family with study; autonomy, community; a sense of belonging; motivation; course design; and support structures at an institutional and teacher level (Blackmon & Major, 2012; Brown et al., 2015; Buck, 2016; Holder, 2007; Zembylas, Theodorou, & Pavlakis, 2008).

With this theme being considered, a Student Forum that focuses on sharing tips and practices for effective learning both in the virtual environment and through self-learning digital modules would allow students to optimize learning in the new normal. Future educators should be able to grasp all the key considerations to be taken into account when learning online or through modules.

Theme 2: Coping Strategies in the New Normal. This theme covers subthemes: self-esteem and mental health. This indicates that students experienced the common challenges and problems with mental health during the new normal. The new normal set forth a lot of sudden changes which were challenging to students, especially those students with low self-esteem and poor self-efficacy. These challenges include anxiety due to technical problems, the lack of enough time for self-development, the time required to answer and manage modules and to upload or submit their content, and the difficulty in adapting to one's varying levels of using technology (Bower, Dalgarno, Kennedy, Lee, & Kenney, 2015; Rasheed, Kamsin, & Abdullah, 2020). These, among others, overwhelmed the students and demanded abrupt adjustments to be done on their end, which had taken a toll on students' mental health, and thus, required students to have coping mechanisms.

The stressful life changes have been documented in both adults and youngsters. A significant proportion of school-aged children and adolescents are experiencing psychological distress during the pandemic (Zhang et al., 2020; Voitsidis, 2020). Indeed, the changes in learning delivery compromised the mental health of many people, and the answer to ensuring students can still cope with the specific situational demands of their course would depend on students' life skills, values system, and resilience. Emotion-focused coping mechanisms could be taught to students through a Student Forum to address and control tendencies for depression, anxiety, self-doubt, and frustrations (Gan, 2006).

Theme 3: Student-Teacher Engagement. This has sub-themes, "Teaching strategies" and "Evaluating online learning". For education students, being adept with the pedagogy in the new normal setup and mastering digitalized or ICT-integrated assessments will help prepare them for the demands of the profession.

Student engagement can be defined as "a student's emotional, behavioral and cognitive connection to their study" which has a direct impact on student success and achievement (Kahu et al., 2013, p. 523). To ensure retention and graduation on online delivered programs, it is important to understand student engagement in the online context (Woodley & Simpson, 2014). Meanwhile, teacher engagement with students can ensure the delivery of quality education. When teachers and students are actively engaged, they seek out new ideas and best teaching practices, regularly monitor students provided and provide immediate feedback, as well as adjust their instruction to the needs of the students.

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Digital technology inherently affects all aspects of student experience, especially the teacher and student engagement in the classroom (Barak, 2018; Henderson, Selwyn, & Aston, 2017; Selwyn, 2016). Hence, designing a Student Forum to help students expand their repertoire of teaching strategies and strengthen their skills in writing diagnostic, formative, summative, and alternative assessments during the new normal will be highly beneficial to them.

Themes 4 & 5: Time Management and Scholarships. The fourth and fifth themes with 3.70% and 1.85% respectively are “Time management” and “Scholarships”. Time management is a very important skill teachers and students alike must master to achieve academic success in their academic endeavors (Kelly, 2004). However, managing time is a challenge the students have to overcome daily. A Student Forum to equip students with strategies for effective time management and new routines that support self-care while achieving goals will greatly help the students.

Scholarships, on the other hand, are important to students since they provide an opportunity for people to earn an education, especially in the teacher education program. Several researchers had concluded that success in higher education is commonly defined by students' persistence, progression, and timely graduation. Financial aid or scholarships both need- or merit-based could facilitate student success (Chen & DesJardis, 2008; Gross et al., 2007; Singell, 2004).

With the rising cost of studying in the new normal, considering the need for fast internet connection, educational gadgets, and equipment, etc, scholarships such as Unified Student Financial Assistance for Tertiary Education (UniFAST) Tertiary Education Subsidy (TES) program could help college students get through their college journey during the pandemic. If students could be oriented and referred to other scholarship grants that can financially aid their studies, then it would significantly help them.

Preferred delivery modality by the SED students in the new normal

Table 3 summarizes the frequency and percentage of the preferred learning modality by the SED students. Face-to-face modality is preferred by 61.29% of the respondents, followed by blended learning with 30.64%, virtual classes with 4.84%, and modular instruction with 3.23%. The results reveal face-to-face to be the most preferred, while modular instruction to be the least preferred modality.

Table 3. Summary of the preferred learning modality by the SED Students

Modality	<i>f</i>	%
Face-to-Face	38	61.29
Virtual Classes	3	4.84
Modular Instruction	2	3.23
Blended Learning	19	30.64

Face-to-face learning modality, the traditional type of learning instruction, is when lesson contents are being delivered in-person to a group of learners, which allows live interaction between teachers and students. Students may prefer face-to-face learning since they have been accustomed to it throughout their school life. With face-to-face learning, students need not bother with a lot of technical preparations which require a certain level of computer skills and equipment necessary for online instruction (McGovern, 2004).

According to Haavind (2000), it is more difficult to monitor student progress and comprehension in an online environment compared to a classroom setting. Teachers must be skilled at tracking student progress with online learning management systems such as Google Classroom. Teachers must be highly skilled at ICT to smoothly navigate the digital world.

Gibson (2008) conducted a study comparing face-to-face learning with online learning and found out that students in the face-to-face sectors have slightly better test scores than online students. Meanwhile, Chen and Jones (2007) did another comparative study and discovered that the final learning outcomes from two classes, one taught face-to-face while the other taught primarily online, were similar. Therefore, in terms of learning outcomes and scholastic scores, the differences are very minimal. However, online learning can be challenging to students since interaction with their instructors is very limited.

The second most preferred modality is Blended learning (BL). Blended learning is an integration of face-to-face and online instruction (Graham, 2013) which has been adopted by higher education institutions across the globe. It has been dubbed as the “new traditional model” or the “new normal” by Ross and Gage (2006) and Norberg et al. (2011). It considers the strengths of digital technology coupled with the traditional face-to-face modality (or other modalities). Consequently, the Department of Education (DepEd) defined Blended learning as face-to-face with any or a mix of online distance learning, modular distance learning, and TV/Radio-based instruction.

This modality, being the second most preferred, would mean that the students are ready to embrace blended learning initiatives and support this innovation in the teaching-learning process in the new normal. Blended learning is a very promising modality that was found to improve students’ success, satisfaction, and sense of community (Dziuban & Moskal, 2011; Means et al., 2013; Rovai & Jordan, 2004). Students can be learning on-campus and off-campus at the same time; hence, they can maximize their learning. However, lack of access to educational technologies can be a challenge in the implementation of this novel educational modality (Fairlie, 2004; Jones et al., 2009).

The least preferred modality is Modular instruction. Under this instruction, materials can be printed or in digitized form (Department of Education, 2020). The results are intriguing as the respondents preferred other learning modalities over modular instruction. The Department of Education Secretary, Leonor Briones (as cited by Magsambol, 2020) announced that 8.8 million parents (or 39.6%) preferred printed modules over blended learning (3.9 parents) and online learning (3.8 parents) for the school year 2020-2021. This preference is due to modules being highly convenient for more of the typical Filipino students. This result shows the disparity in views among students of tertiary education and parents of learners under basic education.

The modular approach may be a good alternative since it is student-centered, self-paced, and requires no note-taking. Cheng and Bakar (2017) cited that the use of a module presents a more flexible learning environment for both instructors and learners. However, several studies have already been conducted about modular instruction as a learning modality. Researchers were able to enumerate obstacles to learning under this modality, which includes insufficient technical equipment (Alvarez, 2020) in the reproduction of modules, and the failure to consider sociocultural aspects (Karsenti & Collin, 2012) in the writing of modules.

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Students likes and dislikes with the learning delivery that could maximize their learning engagement

Figure 3 presents the overview of the thematic chart on what the students like about the learning delivery modality being implemented in Academic Year 2020-2021. Three major themes were recorded: learning modality (56.45%), the teacher (25.81%), and personal development (9.68%). Several students (8.06%) responded with none. Per theme, sub-themes were also recorded.

Figure 3. Overview of the thematic chart on what the student like about the learning delivery modality

Matrix 2 presents the qualitative themes on what the students like about the learning delivery modality being implemented in Academic Year 2020-2021. Sample verbatim responses presented to support the themes and subthemes.

Matrix 2. Summary of qualitative themes on what the student like about the learning delivery modality

Themes	Sub-themes	Theme/ Sub-theme example
Learning Modality	Home-based	<i>"The fact that we are just in our houses"</i>
	Online submission	<i>"Answering activity in google classroom"</i>
	Online Classes	<i>"Having interesting virtual classes"</i>
	Flexible time schedule	<i>"I can take a small break when I feel tired"</i>
	Exploratory learning	<i>"Answering the activities without discussion. So students can explore/ find to understand on how to answer it."</i>
	Convenient	<i>"convenient"</i>
	Technology integration	<i>"Using some social media sites"</i>
The Teacher	Teachers' passion	<i>"It is when the teacher elaborate the topic with fascination and passion"</i>
	Teachers' determination	<i>"Teachers who are doing their very best to ensure that student can learn a lot during their lesson. Whole year of virtual class and my favorite is Ms. Miras, she is an amazing teacher. She made us love online classes more! Plus, she has a lot of activities!"</i>
	Student-teacher interaction	<i>"The best thing about online classes is the interaction between students and teachers, ..."</i>
Personal Development	Overcoming challenges	<i>"Students will challenge to study hard because we tent to rely on the Internet"</i>
	Continuous learning	<i>"I can keep on learning even if I cannot go to school"</i>
	Self-motivation learning	<i>"Like in online classes in to have a clear internet connection and I used my self to motivate and still fighting."</i>
	Development of computer literacy	<i>"The student become literate in using computers and gadgets."</i>
None		<i>"Nothing. I prefer f2f"</i>

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Learning Modality. Students like the learning modality for any of the following reasons extracted from their responses: home-based, online submissions, online classes, flexible time schedule, exploratory learning, convenience, and technology integration. The results show that students generally see the convenience, freedom, flexibility, and accessibility of the modality; that regardless of time and space, students can learn and explore independently in the comforts of their homes and in their own time. These appealing factors provide students accountability for their own learning and full control of their time. They do not need to travel to-and-fro or to secure boarding houses to attend classes. According to Nardo (2017), students benefit from learning when they are taught how to learn when they are empowered. They develop a sense of responsibility in fulfilling their tasks. They are given more choices and are self-paced.

Another likeability of the learning modality being offered is its potential to bank on Gen Z's tech-savviness by integrating technology in the lessons. Given that the education students are 21st-century learners, the learning modalities are giving students a venue to develop their 21st-century skills which include ICT-related literacies. Hence, students can easily adapt to online submissions

and online classes as long as the internet, power, and gadgets are readily available. They are not new to ICT since the youth of today, and even the younger ages, are using the Internet more (Hoofft-Graadl, 2018).

Theme 2: The Teacher. Three sub-themes were revealed, namely: Teachers' Passion, Teachers' Determination, and Student-Teacher Interaction. The role of teachers had been redefined in the new normal. Garg and Prasad (2005) opined that teachers' role in a distance education system differs significantly from a teacher in a traditional system. A lot of things had been reconsidered: the pedagogy, assessment, feedbacking, grading, among others. This re-imagining, coupled with the demands of adopting technology in education, demands teachers' resilience, determination, passion, and commitment. Not only will teachers be adapting to changes, but they also have to personalize learning, customize learning resources, upskill themselves, and come up with innovative teaching strategies for learners. Their role from being facilitators of learning evolved to content creators and innovators.

The respondents were able to take notice of their teachers' passion and determination in delivering the lessons online or through modules. A respondent even noted that "teachers are doing their best." Students' appreciation of the teachers' efforts shows that students know the challenges being faced by teachers in the new normal, and they can see how teachers strive to continuously learn, unlearn and relearn to improve themselves.

Theme 3: Personal Development. This has the following sub-themes: Overcoming challenges, Continuous learning, Self-motivation for learning, and Development of computer literacy. These responses prove that students like how they are developing personally by mastering life skills, strengthening their attitudes, growing their mindset, and enhancing their computer literacy. These skills, values, and attitudes they are developing will contribute to their professional development in their teaching career.

The new normal education tested students' learning management skills, determination, and resilience. Learners' emotional resilience or the ability to generate positive emotions and recover quickly from negative emotional experiences (Davidson, 2000; Conway & McDonough, 2006) will enable students to keep their self-motivation high while facing adversity. This resilience led students to develop coping mechanisms in stressful situations, hence, they continued learning and overcame challenges along the way.

Figure 4 presents the overview of the thematic chart on what the students dislike about the learning delivery modality being implemented in Academic Year 2020-2021. Three major themes were recorded: personal experience (48.39%), online instruction/class (35.48%), and poor quality of learning (14.52%). Several students (1.61%) responded with none. Per theme, sub-themes were also recorded.

Figure 4. Overview of the thematic chart on what the student dislike about the learning delivery modality

Matrix 3 presents the summary of qualitative themes on what the students dislike about the learning delivery modality being implemented in the Academic Year 2020-2021. Sample verbatim responses presented to support the themes and subthemes.

Matrix 2. Summary of qualitative themes on what the student like about the learning delivery modality

Themes	Sub-themes	Theme/ Sub-theme example
Personal Experience	Connectivity/ Signal	"The connection of inter is Unstable and also least of Leaning because we might struggling about the online class"
	Too much screen time	"..., I'm too much exposed to my laptop, ..."
	Task management problem	"... I dont know what to do first"
	Technical Problems	"I am not an expert in manipulating my gadgets and google classroom"
Online Instruction/ Class	Boring	"sometimes it is boring"
	Lack of interaction	"Is when you have a question to your instructor about something regarding to your subject matter, you will still wait for a response through email or in messenger."
	Excessive activities	"Probably, bombarded of different tasks"
	The span of due dates is too short	"The due date of activities isn't enough for me to comply my school works"
Poor Quality of Learning	Difficulty in understanding lessons	"I like least is that having difficulties to understand further topics"
	Lack of feedback	"Lack of feedback. In order to enhance our performance as students, we need feedback on our work."
None		"None"

NOTE: Responses are copied verbatim

Theme 1: Personal Experience. Having the highest among all other recorded themes, the students listed their personal experiences with the learning modality offered during the new normal as their dislike. It covers the following sub-themes: Connectivity/Signal, Too Much Screen Time, Task Management Problems, and Technical Problems. These unpleasant experiences were mainly due to factors beyond students' control.

To maximize learning through online classes and digital access to learning resources, having a strong internet connection is a lot. However, internet problems are common in an internet-challenged country like the Philippines. This is one of the biggest problems apart from the availability of technical gadgets. Pieces of literature point out the needs and challenges of internet connection among students (Aboagye et al., 2021; Chase et al., 2018; Chung et al., 2020a; Lorenzo, 2017).

According to Casillano (2019), in the Philippines, a minimum number of students has internet access, and this impedes their access to e-learning platforms. Since some students live in remote areas where internet connection is not fast or typhoon-prone locations that can disrupt internet connection, students cannot submit requirements on time or attend synchronous online classes. Some students even opt to attend classes in internet cafes (Yra et al., 2020). Indeed, the importance of enhanced internet connection of learning during the new normal cannot be denied, especially in rural areas (Ahmed et al., 2017)

Another issue that can compromise students' physical health and well-being is screen time. The U.S. National Library of Medicine defined screen time as a term used for activities done in front of a screen, such as working on a computer. They added that too much screen time can be harmful to children and adults alike. During the new normal, students spend most of their hours for online classes and answering activities, leaving little to no time for socialization, physical exercises, and outdoor activities.

Because of this new normal, students are compelled to work on their tasks virtually, attend online sessions, access online resources, and communicate online with their peers and instructors. Therefore, students' attention is on their gadgets and technology as they study. Screen time must be limited, controlled, and maintained in moderation among teachers and learners to ensure their health and social well-being.

Theme 2: Online Instruction/Class. Students indicated their dislike of online classes they described as boring, lacking interaction, with excessive activities and due dates. Communicating with their teachers to make arrangements about deadlines of activities was also a challenge because of the "wait time" for teachers to respond since communications now are through emails, texts, and chats. Feedback is therefore limited. And with very minimal student and teacher interaction, students cannot be guided properly and hence, cannot manage their tasks well.

Students raised sentiments on feeling overloaded with excessive activities with very short due dates. This difficulty had been examined by Sundarasan et al. (2020) among the students in Malaysia who claimed they were bombarded with assignments by teachers. The study further revealed that this pressure had a huge impact on the anxiety levels and stress of the learners. The same was the results of a study by Sarvestani et al., (2019) about students complaining about the overwhelming number of modules they have to answer.

Theme 3: Poor Quality of Learning. Students listed two sub-themes: Difficulty in understanding lessons, and Lack of feedback. Students find it hard to understand lessons delivered online or self-learned through modules. During the face-to-face modality, students exhibited their collaborative skills, but during a pandemic, students have to resort to their independent or self-directed learning skills wherein they take charge of their learning. To develop independent learners, critical thinking skills must be considered since it is the framework of independent work.

Several factors could be attributed to poor quality of learning aside from students' poor learning strategies or critical thinking skills. According to Abbasi et al. (2020), the role of instructors is very essential in refining the quality of learning during the pandemic. If teachers are empowered to generate, shape, and incorporate different ideas and practices in the facilitation of the online course content, then learning outcomes could be achieved (Kebritchi et al., 2017). These support the notion that teachers should be prepared, upskilled, and trained to meet the demands of the new normal education through a series of training, webinar, professional learning communities, and linkages, among others.

Furthermore, the lack of immediate feedback provided by teachers to students can be detrimental to students' learning. Without feedback, students will have no idea what they did right or wrong, and the areas they need more improvement. Delayed feedback would result in limited teacher scaffolding. Giving appropriate feedback on time to students can improve the quality of learning (Ellis & Goodyear, 2010).

CONCLUSION

The lectures conducted during the virtual student forum on maximizing online learning through active learners' engagement held last May 7, 2021, has a very high impact on students. The learning outcomes were clear and were attained, the mastery of subject matter was evident, the lecture was presented and delivered well, and the materials used were appropriate. The positive views of students on the forum will pave the way for more student forums in the future.

The success and effectiveness of student fora are dependent on the lined-up topics which must address students' most pressing issues and be tailored to students' needs and aspirations. SED students suggested several topics for the next student forum. They request to be knowledgeable with learning strategies and coping mechanisms they can employ in the new normal setup so that they can be able to adjust to online learning and/or manage modular learning smoothly without compromising their mental health. Being skilled at facilitating student-teacher engagement and time management were also revealed. Some students were also interested in learning more about scholarship opportunities to assist them in their schooling. These promising topics will be considered by the School of Education (SED) faculty and Council of Education Students (CES) in the planning of the future student fora.

Among the four learning modalities being implemented during the new normal, SED students preferred face-to-face learning the most, followed by blended learning. The traditional learning modality, which the students are well accustomed to, offers the most teacher-student interaction, socialization, immediate feedbacking, and application of learning. However, in the new normal, students are willing to innovate and embrace blended learning (limited face-to-face, mixed with other modalities). Virtual and modular instructions are trailing behind, which is an eye-opener to students, faculty, and administrators. These last two modalities are the most commonly offered

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modality in the current system regardless on how the students feel about it. The challenge now is how the teachers, students, and the school community work together to deliver quality education despite obstacles.

SED offers digital offline and online learning modalities. Students can either attend classes via Google Meet video conferencing or do independent studies through modules. Either way, they are to access modules and submit their output online through Google classroom. Students were aware of the advantages of the modalities offered. They like how the modalities are, flexible, convenient, and accessible to them. They also like passionate and determined teachers who made them love online learning due to the meaningful student-teacher interaction inside and outside the virtual classroom. The modalities also allowed for students' personal development; they are harnessing their ICT skills while also strengthening their mental, emotional and social aspects of development.

On the other hand, students' unpleasant personal experiences with an intermittent internet connection, too much screen time which can cause screen fatigue, technical problems, and poor task management make them dislike the current learning modalities offered. Furthermore, some online classes/instructions are boring and activities are overwhelming for students. Several students noted that they have difficulty understanding topics, made worse by delayed or lack of feedback by teachers.

Indeed, students are critical at identifying their likes and dislikes of the learning modalities. The school administration and faculty could come up with various programs to address students' dislikes.

REFERENCE

- Abbasi, Sahar & Ayoob, Tahera & Malik, Abdul & Memon, Shabnam. (2020). Perceptions of students regarding E-learning during Covid-19 at a private medical college. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 36. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.36.COVID19-S4.2766>.
- Aboagye E., Yawson, J.A., & Appiah, K.N. (2021). COVID-19 and e-learning: the challenges of students in a tertiary institution. *Social Education Research*, 2(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.37256/ser.212021422>
- Allen D., & Tanner K. (2005). Infusing Active Learning into the Large-enrollment Biology Class: Seven Strategies, from the Simple to Complex. *Cell Biology Education*, 4, 262–268.
- Alvarez, A. Jr. (2020). The phenomenon of learning at a distance through emergency remote teaching amidst the pandemic crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 144-153. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3881529>
- Armbruster, P., Patel, M., Johnson, E., & Weiss, M. (2009). Active learning and student-centered pedagogy improve student attitudes and performance in introductory biology. *CBE-Life Sciences Education*, 8(3), 203-213.
- Barak, M. (2018). Are digital natives open to change? Examining flexible thinking and resistance to change. *Computers & Education*, 121, 115–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.01.016>.
- Biggs, J. (1999). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*. Buckingham: SRHE and Open University Press.
- Blackmon, S. J., & Major, C. (2012). Student experiences in online courses: A qualitative research synthesis. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 13(2), 77–85.
- Bloxham, S. & Boyd, P. (2007). *Developing Effective Assessment in Higher Education: A Practical Guide*. McGraw-Hill International.

- Bower, M., Dalgarno, B., Kennedy, G. E., Lee, M. J., & Kenney, J. (2015). Design and implementation factors in blended synchronous learning environments: Outcomes from a cross-case analysis. *Computers & Education*, **86**, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2015.03.006>0360-1315
- Brennan J. & Williams, R. (2004) *Collecting and Using Student Feedback. A Guide to Good Practice*. York: Learning and Teaching Support Network. http://hear.ac.uk/assets/documents/resources/database/id352_collecting_and_using_student_feedback_a_guide_to_good_practice.pdf
- Brown, M., Hughes, H., Keppell, M., Hard, N., & Smith, L. (2015). Stories from students in their first semester of distance Learning. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, **16**(4), 1–17.
- Buck, S. (2016). In their own voices: Study habits of distance education students. *Journal of Library & Information Services in Distance Learning*, **10**(3–4), 137–173. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533290X.2016.1206781>.
- Butler, D. L. & Winne, P. H. (1995). 'Feedback and self-regulated learning: A theoretical synthesis', *Review of Educational Research*, **65**(3), 245-281.
- Casillano, N.F.B. (2019). Challenges of implementing an e-learning platform in an internet struggling province in the Philippines. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, **12**(10), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2019/v12i10/137594>
- Chase, T.J.G., Julius, A., Chandan, J.S., Powell, E., Hall, C.S., Phillips, B.L., Burnett, R., Gill, D., & Fernando, B. (2018). Mobile learning in medicine: An evaluation of attitudes and behaviors of medical students. *BMC Medical Education*, **18**(152), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-018-1264-5>
- Chen, C. and Jones, K. (2007, January). Blended Learning vs. Traditional Classroom Settings: Assessing Effectiveness and Student Perceptions in an MBA Accounting Course [Electronic version]. *The Journal of Educators Online*. **4**(1).
- Chen, R. & DesJardins, S. L. (2008). Exploring the effects of financial aid on the gap in student dropout risks by income level, *Research in Higher Education*, **49**(1), 1–18.
- Cheng, M B Bakar (2017) *The Impact of Using Modules in the Teaching and Learning of English in Malaysian Polytechnics: An Analysis of the Views and Perceptions of English Language Teaching*. Jabatan Pengajian Am
- Chinedu E. (2008). Seven Benefits of Internet Forums. *Ezine Articles* <http://ezinearticles.com/?Seven-Benefits-of-Internet-Forums&id=1813184>
- Chung E., Subramaniam, G., & Dass, L.D. (2020a). Online learning readiness among university students in Malaysia amidst COVID-19. *Asian Journal of University Education*, **16**(2), 46-58. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v16i2.10924>
- Conway A.M. and McDonough, S.C. (2006). Emotional resilience in early childhood: Developmental antecedents and relations to behavior problems. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. **1094**(1), 72–77.
- Covic, T. & Jones, M. K. (2008). 'Is the essay resubmission option a formative or a summative assessment and does it matter as long as the grades improve?' *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, **33**(1), 75-85.
- Davidson R.J (2000). Affective style, psychopathology, and resilience: Brain mechanisms and plasticity. *Am Psychol*. **55**(11), 1196–214.
- de Lima, D.P.R., Gerosa, M.A., Conte, T.U. et al. (2019). What to expect, and how to improve online discussion forums: the instructors' perspective. *J Internet Serv Appl* **10**, 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13174-019-0120-0>
- Denson, N., Loveday, T. & Dalton, H. (2010). Student evaluation of courses: what predicts satisfaction? *Higher Education Research & Development*, **29**(4), 339–356.

Evaluation of the SED Student Forum on Maximizing Online Learning through Active Learners' Engagement: The Student Experience

- Dietz-Uhler, B., & Hurn, E. J. (2013). Using learning analytics to predict (and improve) student success: A faculty perspective. *Journal of Interactive Online Learning*, **12**(1), 1541-4914.
- Dziuban, C., & Moskal, P. (2011). A course is a course is a course: Factor invariance in student evaluation of online, blended and face-to-face learning environments. *The Internet and Higher Education*, **14**(4), 236–241.
- El-Halees. (2011). Mining Opinions in User Generated Contents to Improve Course Evaluation. *Software Engineering and Computer Systems*. 107–115.
- Ellis, R. & Goodyear, Peter. (2010). *Students' Experiences of E-Learning in Higher Education: The Ecology of Sustainable Innovation*. 10.4324/9780203872970.
- Fairlie, R. (2004). Race and the digital divide. *The B.E. Journal of Economic Analysis & Policy*, **3**(1). <https://doi.org/10.2202/1538-0645.1263>.
- Feldon, DF (2010) *Why magic bullets don't work*. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning* **42**, 15-21.
- Fink, D.L. (2003). *Creating Significant Learning Experiences: An Integrated Approach to Designing College Courses*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Fry H, Ketteridge S, Marshall S (2002) *A Handbook for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* (2nd edition) London: Routledge.
- Gan Y, Zhang Y, Wang X, Wang S & Shen X. (2006) The coping flexibility of neurasthenia and depressive patients. *Pers Individ Differ*. **40**(8), 59–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2005.09.006>
- Garg, S. and Prasad.V.S. (2005) *Best Practices in Open and Distance Education*, GRADE, Dr. BRAOU, Hyderabad
- Gegenfurtner, A., Fisch, K., and Ebner, C. (2019a). *Teilnahmemotivation nicht-traditionell Studierender an wissenschaftlicher Weiterbildung: Eine qualitative Inhaltsanalyse im Kontext von Blended Learning*. Beiträge zur Hochschulforschung.
- Gegenfurtner, A., Spagert, L., Weng, G., Bomke, C., Fisch, K., Oswald, A., et al. (2017). LernCenter: Ein Konzept für die Digitalisierung berufsbegleitender Weiterbildungen an Hochschulen. *Bavarian J. Appl. Sci*. **3**, 234-243. <https://doi.org/10.25929/z26v-0x88>
- Gibson J. (2008). A Comparison of Student Outcomes and Student Satisfaction in Three MBA Human Resource Management Classes Based on Traditional vs. Online Learning, *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*, **5**(8), 1-10
- Graham, Charles. (2013). *Emerging practice and research in blended learning*.
- Gross, J. P. K., Hossler, D., & Ziskin, M. (2007). Institutional aid and student persistence: an analysis of the effects of institutional financial aid at public four-year institutions, *Journal of Student Financial Aid*, **37**(1), 28–39
- Haavind, S. (2000, Fall). *Why Don't Face-to-Face Teaching Strategies Work in the Virtual Classroom?* [Electronic version]. The Concord Consortium. 4(3).
- Hattie, J. & Timperley, H. (2007). 'The power of feedback', *Review of Educational Research*, **77**(1), 81-112.
- Henderson, M., Selwyn, N., & Aston, R. (2017). What works and why? Student perceptions of 'useful' digital technology in university teaching and learning. *Studies in Higher Education*, **42**(8), 1567–1579. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2015.1007946>.
- Holder, B. (2007). An investigation of hope, academics, environment, and motivation as predictors of persistence in higher education online programs. *The Internet and Higher Education*, **10**(4), 245–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2007.08.002>.
- Hooft Graafl and, J. (2018), *New technologies and 21st century children: Recent trends and outcomes*, OECD Education Working Papers, No. 179, OECD Publishing, Paris, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/e071a505-en>.

- Johnson, C. L., and Schumacher, J. B. (2016). Does webinar-based financial education affect knowledge and behavior? *J. Ext.* **54**, 1–10.
- Jones, S., Johnson-Yale, C., Millermaier, S., & Pérez, F. S. (2009). U.S. college students' internet use: Race, gender and digital divides. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, **14**(2), 244–264 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2009.01439.x>.
- Kahu, E. R. (2013). *Framing student engagement in higher education*. *Studies in Higher Education*, **38**(5), 758–773. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2011.598505>.
- Karsenti, Thierry & Collin, Simon. (2013). Using IT for Distance Learning: Benefits and Challenges for African Learners. *Teachers & Training*. **20**, 13-25.
- Kebritchi, Mansureh & Lipschuetz, Angie & Santiago, Lilia. (2017). Issues and Challenges for Teaching Successful Online Courses in Higher Education: A Literature Review. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*. **46**, 4-29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239516661713>.
- Kelly, M. (2004). Get time on your side. *Careers & Universities*, **24**(4), 28-32.
- Lim, C. P. & Chai, C. S. (2004). An activity-theoretical approach to research of ICT integration in Singapore schools: orienting activities and learner autonomy. *Computers & Education*, **43**(3), 215–236.
- Lorenzo, A.R. (2017). Comparative study on the performance of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE) students in educational technology using blended learning strategy and traditional face-to-face instruction. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, **16**(3), 36-46. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1152658>
- Magsambol, B. (2020) *8.8 Million Parents Prefer Modular Learning for Students—DepEd* [Web Log Post]. <https://www.rappler.com/nation/dep-ed-says-parents-prefer-modular-learning-students>
- Marra, R. M., Moore, J. L. & Klimczak, A. K. (2004). Content analysis of online discussion forums: a comparative analysis of protocols. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, **52**(2), 23–40.
- McGovern, G. (2004, June). *Teaching Online vs. Face-to-Face*. [Electronic version]. CLENExchange, Newsletter of American Library Association Continuing Education Network & Exchange Roundtable. **20**(4).
- Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., & Baki, M. (2013). The effectiveness of online and blended learning: A meta-analysis of empirical literature. *Teachers College Record*, **115**(3), 1–47.
- Nardo, M. T. B. (2017, October 20). Modular Instruction Enhances Learner Autonomy. *Sciepub*. <http://pubs.sciepub.com/education/5/10/3/index.html#:~:text=The%20use%20of%20modules%20is,in%20doing%20their%20individual%20tasks.&text=It%20directs%20students%20to%20practice%20or%20rehearse%20information,-To%20gain%20mastery>
- Nicol, D. J. & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). 'Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: a model and seven principles of good feedback practice', *Studies in Higher Education*, **31**(2), 199-218
- Norberg, A., Dziuban, C. D., & Moskal, P. D. (2011). A time-based blended learning model. *On the Horizon*, **19**(3), 207–216. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10748121111163913>.
- Price, M., Handley, K., Millar, J. & O'Donovan, B. (2010). 'Feedback all that effort but what is the effect?' *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, **35**(3), 277-289.
- Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., & Abdullah, N. A. (2020). Challenges in the online component of blended learning: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, **144**, 10370.
- Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., & Abdullah, N. A. (2020). Challenges in the online component of blended learning: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, **144**, 10370.

Evaluation of the SED Student Forum on Maximizing Online Learning through Active Learners' Engagement: The Student Experience

- Rogers, E. M. (2010). Diffusion of innovations. Simon and Schuster. Vonderwell, S., & Turner S. (2005). Active learning and preservice teachers' experiences in an online course: a case study. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, **13**(1), 65-84
- Ross, B., & Gage, K. (2006). *Global perspectives on blended learning: Insight from WebCT and our customers in higher education*. In C. J. Bonk, & C. R. Graham (Eds.), *Handbook of blended learning: Global perspectives, local designs*, 155–168. San Francisco: Pfeiffer.
- Rovai, A. P., & Jordan, H. M. (2004). Blended learning and sense of community: A comparative analysis with traditional and fully online graduate courses. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, **5**(2), 1–13.
- Sarvestani, M. S., Mohammadi, M., Afshin, J. & Raeisy, J. (2019). Students' experiences of e-Learning challenges: A phenomenological study. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Virtual Learning in Medical Sciences*, **10**(3), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.30476/IJVLMS.2019.45841>
- Seethamraju, R. (2014). Effectiveness of Using Online Discussion Forum for Case Study Analysis. *Education Research International*, Article ID 589860, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/589860>
- Selwyn, N. (2016). Digital downsides: Exploring university students' negative engagements with digital technology. *Teaching in Higher Education*, **21**(8), 1006–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2016.1213229>.
- Siewiorek, A., and Gegenfurtner, A. (2010). *Leading to win: the influence of leadership style on team performance during a computer game training*. in *Learning in the Disciplines: ICLS2010 Proceedings*, Vol. 1, eds K. Gomez, L. Lyons, and J. Radinsky (Chicago, IL: International Society of the Learning Sciences, 524–531.
- Singell, L. D. (2004). Come and stay a while: does financial aid affect retention conditioned on enrollment at a large public university? *Economics of Education Review*, **23**(5), 459–471
- Sundarasan, S., Chinna, K., Kamaludin, K., Nurunnabi, M., Baloch, G. M., Khoshaim, H. B., Hossain, S. F. A. & Sukayt, A (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 and lockdown among university students in Malaysia: Implications and policy recommendations. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, **17**(17), 6206. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176206>
- Suter E, Mandin H, Parker S (1998) *The sciences in the education of Physicians*. *Basic Science Educator*. **8**, 7-9.
- Voitsidis P, Gliatas I, Bairachtari V, Papadopoulou K, Papageorgiou G, Parlapani E. (2020). Insomnia during the COVID-19 pandemic in a greek population. *Psychiatry Res*. 289:113076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113076>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher mental process*.
- Wang, S.-K., and Hsu, H.-Y. (2008). Use of the webinar tool (Elluminate) to support training: the effects of webinar-learning implementation from student-trainers' perspective. *J. Interact. Online Learn*. **7**, 175–194.
- Williams, J. & Kane, D. (2009). 'Assessment and feedback: Institutional experiences of student feedback, 1996 to 2007', *Higher Education Quarterly*, **63**(3), 264-286.
- Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., and Hattie, J. (2020). The Power of Feedback Revisited: A Meta-Analysis of Educational Feedback Research. *Frontier in Psychology*, **10**, Article 3087. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087>
- Woodley, A., & Simpson, O. (2014). *Student dropout: The elephant in the room, Online distance education: Towards a research agenda*, 459–484. Canada: Athabasca University.
- Yorke, M. (2003). 'Formative assessment in higher education: Moves towards theory and the enhancement of pedagogic practice', *Higher Education*, **45**(4), 477-501.
- Yra, J.F.P., Castillo, R.H., Bautista, R.G., Camayang, J.G., & Camayang, A.G.G. (2020). Students' online learning readiness and internet connectivity: Bases for the customization of QSU e-Aral. *American Journal of Educational Research*, **8**(11), 878-894. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-8-11-8>

- Zembylas, M., Theodorou, M., & Pavlakis, A. (2008). The role of emotions in the experiences of online Learning: Challenges and opportunities. *Educational Media International*, 45(2), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523980802107237>.
- Zhang Z, Zhai A, Yang M, Zhang J, Zhou H, Yang C. (2020). Prevalence of depression and anxiety symptoms of high school students in Shandong province during the COVID-19 epidemic. *Front Psychiatry*. 11:1499. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.570096>